

EDITORIAL AND DIDACTIC CAPABILITIES OF PROGRAM SOFTWARE FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INFORMATION CULTURE

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Abstract. *The given article presents information regarding culture that consists of acquiring certain knowledge and skills in the field of information and communication technologies, as well as the content of educational materials, modern mass media pose new problems and challenges for the concept of media literacy, and require society to form appropriate skills and competencies. Education plays a key role in the formation of information culture, but also implies knowledge of legal and ethical norms and rules and compliance with them.*

Keywords: *information, culture, process, innovative, modern, technology, information, professional, culture, development, self*

Introduction. It is important to note that in the field of innovation in education, the purpose, content, methods, forms and tools of teaching, as well as the structure that includes lesson plans (developments), are understood. Modeling is one of the basic technological methods of systematic analysis when studying complex, multi-component systems. Their operation is defined by both internal and external factors. Modeling, as a scientific research method, is widely used in pedagogy. Along with cognitive methods such as observation and experimentation, modeling plays a significant role.

Definitely, modeling allows us to dive deeply into the subject matter of the research object. Specialists define modeling as the process of creating layered models, where the real, existing system is modeled from various perspectives and with different tools. This method is considered an integrated approach, which allows for combining both empirical and theoretical considerations in pedagogical research, and provides the opportunity to merge logic-based structures and scientific abstractions with practical experience in the study of pedagogical objects.

Certainly, the aforementioned considerations in the use of the modeling method help in systematizing knowledge about the phenomena or processes being studied, offering ways to describe them with integrated patterns, defining clearer relationships between the components, and opening opportunities for creating unified classifications. Experts identify the system of elements reflecting the links, relationships, and functions of the research object in the form of a model. The model is implemented based on a certain alignment between the original object and its model, which is not exactly the same but similar, and the process of implementation is carried out in this way.

Besides that, the main feature of the theoretical model is that it expresses the interrelationship of components at a certain level and incorporates a certain structure that reflects internal, important relationships. The development of the model for improving the information culture of 10-11th grade students is based on competencies and contextual approaches, the goals of which and pedagogical system structures were discussed in the previous sections.

The model for improving the information culture of 10-11th grade students in the context of innovative education includes the content of the model, which involves not only classroom activities but also independent work, the creation of a lifestyle for educational institutions, and the establishment of a community oversight system among students. These tasks aim to develop all areas of the educational institution's activities and include pedagogical approaches based on active collaboration, practical methods for teaching, and the use of competency-based educational tools. The core of these methods is linked to the understanding of knowledge in relation to these approaches.

Additionally, in the process of improving the information culture of high school students, the analysis of the relationship between the teaching staff of the educational organization and the reforms being implemented in the country was conducted. In the process of giving students knowledge, priority was given to fostering professional creativity, independent thinking, and initiative, ensuring content continuity, and social effectiveness through practical methods, which culminated in the creation of a working model for its application.

Methodology. This model, based on innovative approaches, aims to enhance the information culture of high school students through their interaction with the environment, the development of human qualities, and the acquisition of self-development skills. The model for improving the information culture of 10-11th grade students was realized through practical trials. Our task is to create a software program for the development of foundational competencies in 10-11th grade students and apply it in practice, with a focus on continuous improvement. To achieve this, we studied the task set before us based on three principles:

1. In the first phase, we jointly analyzed the software program.
2. To improve the development of the software for 10-11th grade students, we implemented improvements by considering the integration within the subject system and its application in production.
3. In the process of improving the foundational competencies of 10-11th grade students, we created an electronic program. We demonstrated the application of teaching principles and problem-solving methods based on our program in both classroom and extracurricular activities. The expected effectiveness of the program was that, by improving the software for the development of foundational competencies, we were able to provide students with the opportunity to choose a profession, organize a preparation system for them, and achieve high efficiency. In our program, we substantiated the stages of planning and implementation.

Surprisingly, in the program's development phase, the subject matter is clarified, tools for the educational environment are selected (such as Moodle, Zoom, etc.), the type of lesson, its goal, content, and key concepts and terms (related to the lesson process) are determined. The program considers students' interests in the subject, their thinking, worldview, and abilities, and sets the expected outcomes. Pedagogical, psychological, and technological concepts, as well as information technologies, multimedia tools, slides, and digital educational environments, are selected for use during lessons.

Certainly, in the curriculum preparation (design) phase, the content of the teaching materials aligned with the subject is developed, key concepts are structured in lesson stages, and the activities for students at each stage are clarified. Methods, pedagogical and technical knowledge, information technologies, multimedia tools, and the use of slides and digital

educational environments are considered to achieve the expected results. The lesson plan and technological map are created.

Definitely, the implementation and execution phase refers to the educational activity and lesson process, where the teacher, following the lesson plan and technological map, applies the developed curriculum. At this stage, it is essential for the teacher to avoid errors, ensuring that students acquire the necessary concepts, knowledge, skills, and competencies that form their foundational competencies.

This process consists of four stages: introduction to the topic, forming new concepts and knowledge, reinforcing concepts and knowledge, and summarizing the results. The lesson is conducted using digital educational environments (such as Moodle, Zoom) and focuses on shaping information culture through the use of educational platforms.

In the curriculum design (construction) phase, the goal is clarified, and the structure of the curriculum such as planning the course content, defining the goals, the subject matter, materials, videos, animations, a glossary, slides and the testing of knowledge is organized.

The goal is to ensure individual assessment through tests, quizzes, and feedback based on the subjects taught. The content of the subject is structured around key concepts and terms, and materials for lectures, seminars, assignments, monitoring, and test questions are developed accordingly.

Creating the software product: For developing the pedagogical software tool, various software tools are selected (e.g., Macromedia Dreamweaver, AutoPlay, JavaScript, Turbo C, HTML, Delphi, etc.). The computer text, hypertext structure, and multimedia data are selected, including slides, animations, and visualization materials. Audio is recorded, and the synchronization of the audio is checked.

In the stage of implementing the developed pedagogical software, the tool is introduced and applied in the pedagogical practice. In the final stage, the effectiveness of the developed pedagogical software in the educational process is assessed. In the summary and recommendations phase, the effectiveness of the RTR (Radio Television and Radio) is evaluated, and recommendations for its application are made. These recommendations are then shared with the teachers who will be using the software in their teaching.

Based on the stages of development mentioned above, we created software products and achieved certificates of ownership [79,85]. In the process of creating pedagogical tools and electronic educational resources, the integration of programs occurs as follows [7,8].

Certainly, these technologies can include PHP, JavaScript, HTML, CSS, SQL, and others. HTML, CSS, and JavaScript are used to shape the structure and design of electronic courses. The database and dynamic functionality of the course are designed using SQL and PHP programming languages.

This electronic course is based on SaaS (Software as a Service), and it has all the necessary software and technical capabilities for further development in the future.

At present time many courses aimed at teaching subjects to 10th-11th grade students have been created. These courses and their capabilities differ from each other based on various indicators.

For example, some courses may be paid, while others may be free. In addition, in electronic courses, student assessments and the teaching method can be focused on mandatory step-by-step mastery of the topics.

Table 1.1: Tools used in the creation of the course:

№	Basic program that creates the Pedagogical Software Tool (PST)	Files of materials ensuring the integrity of the PST	Program output/result
1	Moodle in our distance learning system	-text files.doc(x); -graphic files pdf,jpg,jpeg, svg and others -audiofiles mp3,.wav,.ogg,.vma and others. From videofiles mpeg till mpegI .hd,.mp4,.m4v,.mov and others	-distance, didactic base of organizing educational process in Moodle -in our distance learning system, electronic educational resources and pedagogical software tools that help organize the educational process.
2	In our distance learning system, Auto Play Media8, Namoeeditor, Flash, Turbo Saut, and others.	-test files.txt,exe,.swf and others	

Online electronic courses are divided into several types, and they differ based on the students' learning needs, learning styles, and goals. Below are the most common types of electronic courses:

1. Asynchronous Courses (Self-paced learning)

Description: 10-11th grade students study course materials at their own convenient time. The course materials are pre-prepared, and students have the opportunity to access the course and continue learning at any time. Advantages: Full flexibility for learning, allowing students to study based on their own capabilities and without pressure.

Examples: Many courses on platforms like Udemy, Coursera.

2. Synchronous Courses (Real-time learning)

Description: Teachers and students participate in classes simultaneously. Lessons are conducted via webinars or live sessions. Advantages: Provides real-time interaction during the learning process, allowing students to engage in group discussions and question-answer sessions. Examples: Live online classes through platforms like WizIQ, Zoom, or Microsoft Teams.

3. Blended Learning

Description: Combines both online and traditional (offline) learning. Part of the course is conducted online, and part takes place in a physical classroom. Advantages: Combines the benefits of flexible online learning with the advantages of traditional classroom-based learning.

Examples: Many university courses follow a blended learning model.

4. MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses)

Description: Large-scale open courses for a wide range of learners, including masterclasses and interviews with experts. These courses are typically free or low-cost, but a fee is often required

to receive a certificate.
 Advantages: Covers a broad range of topics and is accessible to many students.
 Examples: Platforms like Coursera, edX, and FutureLearn.

5. Gamified Courses

Description: The learning process is made engaging and motivating through game elements, such as points, levels, or game-like tasks. Advantages: Helps 10-11th grade students to develop information literacy, enhances their knowledge, and prepares them for future careers. Examples: Online language learning platforms and quiz-based games are examples of gamified courses. Many online courses for subjects like mathematics or related fields are available on various platforms in the form of gamified courses.

In this context, the course aimed at shaping the cultural and technological practices of 10-11th grade students through the use of software platforms is abbreviated in a relevant way.

Main Features of Electronic Courses: Summary and Comparison

1.2 Table

Platform	Course name	Type	Content type	Format	Price	Certificates
Coursera	"We Study Example Problems in Mathematics" Course	Asynchronous, MOOC	Videos, quiz questions, educational games, problem-based exercises, problems.	Focused on self-directed learning	60 \$	Without certificate
edX	Mathematical understanding of uncertainty	Asynchronous, MOOC	Video, test questions	Focused on self-directed learning	54 \$	Confirmed Certificate
Khan academy	Basics of Mathematics	Asynchronous, MOOC	Video, test questions	Focused on self-directed learning	Free	Without Certificate
Mathematics course	Learning mathematics	Hybrid, MOOC	Video, text of the lecture, presentation, practical task, test questions	Focused on self-directed learning	Free	With Certificate

In contrast, the demand for skilled professionals who can effectively utilize modern computing machines that cover all social sectors is becoming increasingly evident today. It is well known that computer technology, which is considered the fundamental element of computer systems, has played various roles at different stages in the development of programming. As the power of computers and the development of technical tools increase, and as the methods of programming evolve, the complexity of problems that can be solved by computers has also risen. This has led to an increased focus on programming technologies. In recent times, for users to solve their mathematical problems, it is no longer sufficient to only know mathematics, but they must also be proficient in computer operation, at least one programming language, and have mastered complex calculation methods.

Currently, for those who are not proficient in programming or do not have the opportunity to learn it, there are specialized educational software suites, electronic manuals, and typical calculation tools designed for performing specific tasks mathematical operation software packages (ADP) are available. Specifically, some of the most practical computer algebra systems are Mathematica, Maple, Matlab, MathCAD, Derive, and Scientific Workplaces. The first two of these are designed for professional mathematicians, and they stand out due to the broadness of their capabilities and their complexity in use. The Matlab software is designed for working with matrices, automatic control of signals, and iterative processing. MathCAD and derive, on the other hand, are much easier to use, addressing the typical needs of students.

In addition, the Eureka package can also be included in this list. This software provides practical solutions for various classes of computational problems through the MathCAD application package. Today, efficiently and effectively using these tools has become essential for every individual.

The MathCAD software starts with the most basic concepts and progressively covers various practical problems related to solving mathematical models using numerical methods. Detailed instructions on how to fully utilize the capabilities of MathCAD software are provided.

The 21st century is often referred to as the age of spirituality and enlightenment, the era of science, culture, and information. With this in mind, it is not difficult to identify the key features and characteristics of the present age. In fact, the future of Uzbekistan is a bright one. To bring this future closer, it is necessary to develop the intellectual abilities of the youth and enable them to study modern knowledge, science, and the latest technological advancements.

MathCAD software:

MathCAD software provides instructions for fully utilizing its capabilities. The core principle of differentiation is not to constantly simplify the educational material, but to use "tip cards" by the teacher to provide tiered support to students through a layered approach in the learning process. In one example, a solution to a problem is given, while in another, a diagram or graph of the problem is presented as a guide. In another case, the solution to a problem similar to the given template is provided as a reference. As a result, all students work on the same problem during practical sessions, but they are provided with different guidance materials.

Information Culture is a key component of an individual's overall culture, enabling them to handle information: receiving, reproducing, and applying it in practice. For participants in pedagogical activities, developing their own information culture means having qualities that help them understand themselves and find their place in the world. Education plays an important role in shaping an individual's information culture.

Results and discussion. To meet the requirements of the modern information society, a person needs to know how to:

1. Analyze acquired information;
2. Differentiate information based on its importance;
3. Evaluate information according to specific criteria;
4. Effectively utilize information to achieve pedagogical goals.

Information culture is not just about mastering specific knowledge and skills in the field of information and communication technologies, but also about knowing and adhering to legal and ethical norms and rules. [5,6]

In the globe of today, the active implementation of comprehensive information technology platforms in the education system has become extremely important. From this perspective, the increasing number of graduates working with information technologies, artificial intelligence, and big data in school education is becoming a demand of the time. The innovative strategies for professional self-development of modern students are being implemented through the use of advanced information technologies, databases, and remote access to scientific and educational resources.

Table 1.3: The most basic concepts of the MathCAD software.

From a didactic point of view, information culture is often understood as the preparation level necessary for the effective activity of an individual’s group or community. Another approach defines information culture as essential life skills and knowledge, as well as the most important tool for cognition in the process of personal and social development. This definition allows us to consider information culture as the main driving force of lifelong learning. This educational activity is a very effective tool from the perspective of data collection and processing, as well as creating new knowledge. In this approach, the harmony of personal development takes priority. [1,2,3]

Modern pedagogy views information culture from the second approach as a necessary

stage and tool for personal development. In general, information culture plays a central role in the modern information society, enabling people to consciously interact with mass media, analyze information, and make informed decisions. Modern mass media introduces new challenges and trials for media literacy concepts, requiring society to develop the necessary skills and competencies.

Education plays a crucial role in shaping information culture, which is why developing relevant educational programs and methods, as well as incorporating media literacy and information culture courses into university curricula and programs, is of great importance. As an educational process, shaping the concept and methods of teaching information culture and media literacy significantly contributes to fostering critical thinking, cultural literacy, and ethical behavior in the information society. [8,10]

The approach based on innovation for developing information culture in 10-11 grade students is based on the following principles: providing knowledge in harmony with nature, education, pedagogical guidance, adaptability, and creativity; the integration of connections and special tasks for teacher-student dialogues. Let's analyze the understanding of these principles.

The Principle of Conformity to Culture

The essence of this principle is that natural factors play a significant role in human development. For the development of an individual, creating the right conditions and viewing nature as a part of the individual's existence, with respect to its natural powers, is essential. Simply put, in organizing any activity, including information-related activities, it is necessary to consider the natural abilities of students in higher grades. It is incorrect to oppose nature; fighting against it is a waste of time. Establishing information clubs at schools and involving students in them can be a solution to this problem. This allows the internal world of the youth to be connected with external influences in a relevant manner. This process is carried out by adopting an individual approach to the students in the school club. Logically, this leads us to the next principle.

The Principle of Conformity to Information Culture

In the process of shaping information culture, students must become familiar with the various layers of society's culture and adapt to the ongoing changes in their environment while minimizing the negative effects of innovations. Shaping information culture involves familiarizing students with all aspects of culture, humanity's cultural heritage, including science, technology, technological advancements, general culture, and social values. The principle of cultural approach means understanding the deep interrelation between the concepts of "information" and "culture," and that information culture is an inseparable part of general culture. The development of scientific and technical progress, the unprecedented growth of information technology in the information society, and the changes it brings to daily life are essential to the formation of this culture. [3,10]

The interactive activities between the teacher and the students should be based on a dialog of mutual cooperation and the teacher's personal approach. These activities should take into account the students' age and abilities and be structured around the concept of school information resources and the surrounding Internet activities. The process of this activity in higher grade students should be based on forms of mutual interaction designed with the students' potential and capabilities in mind.

The teacher-student dialogue should be driven by the need for cooperation, and mutual activity should be its foundation. In this case, even if the dialogue is conducted with the group, it must still be personalized for each participant.

In summary, the principles of activity we explore should emphasize that the basic rules of activity form the foundation of the process. According to the theoretical foundations of our research, the formation of information culture in students is carried out through a systematic, activity-based, technological, and integrative approach. The concept of "information culture" can be expressed as the level of education in the field of information in higher-grade students, which is essential for effective activity.

The essence of the system approach is reflected in the following principles, which aim to identify the characteristics of the system's objects and improve them. These principles provide the foundation for improving the teaching-learning process in the context of information culture development. [5, 6, 7, 9.]

a) The generality of the system in relation to the external environment, with the system being studied in conjunction with its environment. From this perspective, educational issues form an independent domain, but they are studied in close relation to social and economic development, and the demands of society;

b) The division of the system into constituent parts by identifying general elements. The elements of the system are in complex relationships and mutual activities, and between them, the connection that shapes the system is identified as crucial and is necessary to highlight the most important element for the system. In the "open" educational system, the relationships between the individual and the various conditions and sources of education, and in the "closed" educational system, the "educator-pedagogue" relationships operate as the central connection; [1, 2, 3.]

g) The categories of the pedagogical system reflecting its main elements are as follows: goals, content, conditions, means, actions, development paths, and results;

d) A special method for organizing the relationships between system elements-this is management, which includes setting goals, selecting means, monitoring results, and making reforms.

What is more interesting, activity-based approaches ensuring the principles of the pedagogical model, shaping the student's skills and upbringing, and implementing the gradual and continuous process of developing students' information culture in school extracurricular activities, particularly through the Internet circles. An activity-based approach model helps in shaping the information culture of the student, explaining how libraries, information services, or computers are structured, and familiarizing them with the details of information and computer technologies. This approach isn't just seen from the perspective of the library, but also involves addressing information-related tasks during education, professional development, or in leisure activities. From the consumer's perspective, these tasks need to be structured in a way that is practical and usable. [85]

The essence of the activity-based approach is to study the real process of human interaction with the environment, focusing on solving important tasks for life. In this context, the individual is the subject of mutual activity, operating as an active participant (or the initiator of activity) in a sequential chain of actions.

From the perspective of applying this approach to the issue of shaping information culture, the activity-based approach aims to clarify the essence and structure of this culture, helping students fully assimilate the necessary knowledge. This process involves identifying and describing (depicting) specific actions in the educational context. In addition, the acquisition of

knowledge is directly linked to strengthening particular actions, which, in turn, aids in shaping the students' general abilities and behavioral methods.

Knowledge is not simply obtained in a passive way, but rather integrated into the student's own activities. In this context, the analysis and modeling of the outcomes of activities are important skills that need to be applied during the educational process.

The technological approach aims to provide the necessary methods and tools to shape a person's information culture by utilizing pedagogical technologies. This method involves setting the required parameters to achieve clear and defined outcomes. The process of monitoring and controlling these outcomes ensures that the right results are achieved according to predetermined standards.

Changes within the information society drive the need to develop an individual's information culture. Within the concept of "information culture," four core components can be distinguished, as illustrated in Figure 1.1

Table.1.1

Criteria and Indicators for the Level of Formation of Information Culture

Criteria	Indicators		
Motivational-Value	The degree to which an individual has internalized the information activity and its standards and rules, related to socially significant motivations.		The relevance and diversity of the criteria for evaluating information events from the perspective of their social significance.
Cognitive	The level of formation of the information processing style of thinking	The degree of understanding and comprehension of the social significance of information and information activities, their dialogical nature.	The level of knowledge about oneself, one's abilities, and weaknesses, as well as methods of applying and compensating for them.
Instrumental - Activity-based	The level of mastering information activity and communication methods and tools	The relevance of knowledge in the field of information culture in modern society.	The level of mastering technologies that ensure safety while working with information and the level of mastering the process itself.
Cognitive	The level of alignment with the norms and rules of information activity and interpersonal activity	The level of consciousness and sense of responsibility in selecting the	The level of activity and independence in achieving the goals of one's own information activity and evaluating

		goals of one's own information activity and methods to achieve them.	information events and processes.
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Conclusion. By summerising it should be suggested that there are many examples of teaching mathematics or other subjects related to this field in the form of online electronic courses on various platforms. In this table, the electronic course for ‘10-11 grade students in which the formation of a culture of using program platforms is developed’ is expressed in the relevant abbreviation.

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